

Rigor and Reproducibility Checklist

Maria Machado

Replicability in reporting for:

Methods

Data

Simulations & Models

Graphical Data

Microscopy

Gels & Blots

Cells

Figure Legends

Antibodies

Immunochemistry

Simulations & Models

- ✓ Provide a link to or copy of a working version of the software and code used via a public repository, such as GitHub.
- ✓ GitHub is also integrated with ORCID, which aids in keeping track of versions and identifying the contributing authors.

Microscopy

- ✓ State imaging type (confocal, widefield), microscope setup (make, model), and imaging settings (lenses, filters, camera and/or software for image capture).
 - ✓ Describe how images were processed (changes to intensity and/or contrast).
- ▶ **For confocal images, state what is shown (maximum projections or optical sections).**

Cells

- ✓ Describe source of cells utilized in detail (species, sex, strain, ethnicity/race, age of donor, whether primary or established).
- ✓ Declare whether cell line authentication was performed and by which method (e.g., short tandem repeat profiling).

▶ **Provide RRIDs for each cell and antibody reported in the manuscript.**

Antibodies

- ✓ Report dilutions used for primary and secondary antibodies for all experiments.
- ✓ Provide evidence that validates the specificity of the primary antibody. Reference the published article if data already exist,
- ✓ For Western blots, describe how the samples were prepared and how the data were quantified.

Graphical data

- ✓ Use a format that shows the range of data points (dot plots or box-and-whisker plots) rather than formats that may mask the variability (bar graphs or line graphs).
- ✓ Select colours that can be distinguished by red-green colourblind individuals.
- ✓ If data were normalized, please explain how this was done.

Gels & Blots

- ✓ Insert spaces or dividing lines to indicate if lanes have been moved or deleted and disclose the arrangement in the figure legend.
- ✓ Retain space above and below the band of interest from the original image.
- ✓ Include the precise position of an independent marker of migration (molecular weight marker or nucleotide ladder).

Figure legends

- ✓ Report all statistical tests used and exact p values, when possible. This also applies to p-values provided in the manuscript body.
- ✓ Report n value for each condition in every panel. Indicate number of technical and biological replicates.
- ✓ Report sex or gender, if not stated as only one sex or gender in the Methods.

Immunocytochemistry

- ✓ Describe the controls and their appropriateness.
- ✓ Present a primary control and a secondary control image along with the experimental group images.
- ✓ Include a scale bar.

Adapted from

<https://journals.physiology.org/editorial-policies#rigor>

For human studies and animal experiments, follow the relevant EQUATOR Network guidelines.

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If you would like to know more about SAGER guidelines and the reporting of sex and gender, please see my blog.

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